

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

OPTIMIZATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF A HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHER FOR THE PURPOSE OF PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT PREVENTION

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Abstract

We on the cause of previous burnout analysis found that specific career and strong emotional needs, work pressure and interpersonal relationship disorder, workload, staff and job requirements is not coordinated, do not match, personal characteristics the four easy to cause burnout [1]. Most teachers in higher education work in universities, which should not only educate students and cultivate new students academically, but also play an exemplary role in the education industry. This means that higher education teachers need to deal with a huge interpersonal relationship and do a good job in their work. Preventing job burnout has become the most urgent problem for higher education teachers, and optimizing teaching activities is the best choice. This paper aims to optimize the teaching activities of higher education teachers to prevent job burnout.

Keywords: higher education teachers, pedagogical activity, professional burnout, mental health, optimization of the pedagogical activity, professional burnout prevention.

Reduce unnecessary administrative tasks for teachers in higher education. The excessive rules and regulations of the education system make the higher education teachers exhausted, only to solve the problems caused by the cumbersome administrative procedures and insufficient resource allocation under the system problems. This is also one of the reasons for occupational burnout. Higher education teachers cannot concentrate on their professional ability and creativity. In a 2018 Maccos study on the status of university teachers found that the average number of university teachers worked 48 hours a week. According to the 5 working days per week, the average daily working time is nearly 10 hours. The real weekly working hours of university teachers are more than 4 hours required by law. Twenty-two percent of the surveyed university teachers worked more than 60 hours a week. Even though the working day is Monday to Friday, some college teachers also go home according to the normal work hours, but in fact, many college teachers are still working at home, including their days off, and it is normal for them to stay up late for college teachers.

In 2015, Cornell University's then-president, Elizabeth Garrett, launched an initiative to reduce the administrative burden. As part of the initiative, the College of Arts and Sciences established a dedicated committee. The committee urged a rigorous investigation to "verify" whether the new policies and working procedures would save time and costs. The results show that the "end user" consensus:

- 1) the new program is needed;
- 2) In general, it takes less work than the replaced workflow;

3) No additional processes will be implemented. The administrative work involving research includes travel, procurement, reimbursement, human resources, safety reporting, and progress reporting for funders and management organizations.

Increase interdisciplinary exchanges to break down academic barriers.

In a survey of the staff of Bohai University, we found that. Most higher education teachers believe that one of the most effective teaching activities to prevent job burnout is to increase interdisciplinary communication and break down academic barriers. The traditional academic system leads to the poor communication between disciplines, and limits the exchange of knowledge and the development of interdisciplinary research. This is undoubtedly fatal to the academic blow of higher education teachers. In teaching guidance, academic research and management service, higher education teachers show the characteristics of professional activities of university teachers, which are different from other industries, and pay more attention to academic development and breakthrough experience. However, in real life, research is often mixed with various phenomena and changes, which means that higher education teachers need to find breakthroughs in multiple disciplines. Increasing interdisciplinary communication can not only provide innovative thinking and also increase the enthusiasm of higher education teachers for scientific research.

Increase the professional development opportunities for teachers and pay attention to mental health and safety.

The particularity of the professional activities of teachers in higher education is a complex process,

which includes not only cultivating students' personal quality and academic ability, but also shaping the of teachers' self-quality [2]. We find that in the current social situation, many higher education teachers lack opportunities for professional development, and the unfinished shaping of self-quality and other academic pressures have a negative impact on teachers' mental health, which leads to the decline of work efficiency and happiness of higher education teachers, and then affects the teaching quality and students' development.

Increasing the professional development opportunities for teachers can not only provide high-quality teacher groups for higher education institutions, but also bring about changes to student development. At the same time, mental health and safety cannot be ignored, because psychological problems not only involve work, but also to the family and society. Mental health is generally to adapt to the environment and emotional performance, the opposite will appear adverse effects. Prevention of psychological problems can effectively improve negative emotions and create a positive educational environment and work environment. Institutions of higher education should regularly promote mental health related knowledge and ideas, mental illness related knowledge and ideas, promote their mental health attitude and habits [3].

Conclusion

Optimizing the teaching activities of higher education teachers can prevent job burnout. The education reform of higher education institutions should not only be used in how to train students, but also pay attention to teachers. Higher education teachers, as students and other ties, are crucial.

References

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